

BASIC CONCEPTS OF COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: This article addresses the problems and tasks of cognitive linguistics, the purpose of the work is to show the quintessence linguistics and the concept as its basic concept, as well as the study of linguistic processes, linguistic units and categories in their correlation with memory imagination, perception, and thinking. This research can be continued in the framework of the following topics: taxonomical analyses of concepts and concept spheres in different language, investigations of gender factors reflected in different concepts.

Keywords: linguist and cultural studies, the virtualization of water and fire concepts, analysis of phrase logical units, entho-linguistics, linguo-culturology, and cognitive linguistics.

Introduction: In every science, there have been periods of upheaval and crisis in the history. And this kind of situations demand scientists to look at the object of study with a "new eye" to tackle it from different point of view. At the beginning of the twentieth century the crisis in theoretical physics lasted a long time. As a result, of the application of new process in research, different theories have appeared. First of all, it is a concept, concept and meaning. The most difficult thing is that the problem of their differentiation to solve and debatable in theoretical linguistics is one of the new cognitive sciences, the object of research of which is the nature and essence of knowledge and cognition. Cognitive linguistics is characterized by a commitment to the inseparability of meaning and form in the study of language. It also takes the view that language reflects general aspects of cognition rather than adapting a modular view of mind. This field of science, which has hitherto analyzed the language system and text construction has expanded with concepts and categories related to the activities of perception, cognition, comprehension and analyses. As a result, the collaborate with cognitive science, such as logic, psychology and

cognitive theory is increasing. However, this collaboration help to enrich linguistics itself with another field - cognitive linguistics.

When it comes to emergence of cognitive, in 1950s J .Miller point out the symposium on information theory is of particular importance. The American professor J.J Brunner who is one of the first to give lecture about cognitive process. Mainly in north America the emergence of cognitive linguistics in the 60s and 70s of the twentieth century led to the view semantics as a separate linguistic theory. Thus, the semiotics play very important role in the use of language. The evaluation of cognitive orientation has clearly indicate by American linguistics that traditional methods of semantic expression cannot meet all the illustration of cognitive semantic research. By the last years of the twentieth century, there was a need to approach language from the point of its participation in the human activities thought. Cognitive is a field of science that studies the human thinking, mind, and the mental process and states associated with them.

The tasks of cognitive linguistics include:

1. To determine the role of language in the creation of human knowledge .
2. Revealing issues related to linguistic and cognitive images of the world.
3. Define the relationship between conceptional system and language.

Cognition, a care concept of cognitive linguistics, involves knowledge and thinking within language, so cognition, cognitivism is closely related to linguistics. Today, the study of the relationship between language and other types of human activity has become a general axiom in the entire complex of human science.

Language helps cognitive to understand human behavior more than culture and society. Cognitive linguistics uses operational units of memory , such as, frames, concepts, gestalts, as a research tool. The main term of cognitive linguistics are: intelligence, knowledge, conceptional system, cognition, linguistic worldview, cognitive base, cognitive model, categorization cultural concepts, national cultural area, world image and others. A conceptual is interpreted system is a mental level or mental set based on the some of all the concepts present in the human mind and their experienced combustions. There are four variants of cognitive science:

- description of the mechanisms connecting stimulus, input and output of the human" thinking machine" .
- study of the phenomena of the inner mental nature of a person

- study of the specifics of cognitive processes in comparison with effects.

In conclusion.

Cognitive linguistics complements the analyses of the language with the analyses of speech various contexts of the use of the corresponding lexemes the judgments about the concept recorded in the texts, reference books, proverbs, aphorisms in which the concept is represented.

References

1. Sapir, E. (1929). A study in phonetic symbolism. *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 12(3), 225–239.
2. Qulmamatova Muattar Otabek qizi. (2023). The Role of Concept in Linguistics. *Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies* (2993-2599), 1(10), 50–53. Retrieved from <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/AJRCS/article/view/1861>
3. Ibragimova Hilola Bahodirjon Qizi, & To'lqinova Maftuna Hasan qizi. (2023). DEBATE TECHNOLOGY AS AN INTERACTIVE FORM OF TEARNING IN ENGLISH CLASSES. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 2(4), 56–59. Retrieved from <https://ojs.rmasav.com/index.php/ojs/article/view/966>
4. Qulmamatova Muattar Otabek qizi. (2023). TRANSLATION PROBLEMS OF MEDICAL TERMS. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Education, Technology and Management*, 2(4), 39–46. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7796602>
5. Qulmamatova Muattar Otabek qizi, Safarova Farida Normurotovna (2021). The Features of a Good Translator in Translating Medical Terms. *Analytical journal of education and development*, (2181-2624) <https://www.sciencebox.uz/index.php/ajed/article/view/526/505>
6. Сафарова, Д. А. (2018). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТОПОНИМОВ В РУССКОМ И УЗБЕКСКИХ ЯЗЫКАХ. *Гуманитарный трактат*, (37), 26-27.
7. Akhmedova Adolat Ravshan kizi. (2022). Problems of Formation of Phonetic Competence of Students (A Level 1). *Eurasian Scientific Herald*, 6, 160–162. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/esh/article/view/919>
8. Soatmurodova Shoxista Zafar qizi. (2023). ANALYSIS OF THE BORROWINGS RELATED TO THE FIELD OF “ATTAR” IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and*

Development, 95–97. Retrieved from

<https://www.bjisrd.com/index.php/bjisrd/article/view/966>

9. Ibragimova, H. B. qizi.(2022). INGLIZ TILINI O’QITISHDA PODKASTLAR VA ULARDAN FOYDALANISHNING AMALIY JIHATLARI. Results of National Scientific Research International Journal, 1(8), 212–219. Retrieved from <http://academics.uz/index.php/rnsr/article/view/1118>

10. Tovasharovna, K. G. (2023). The Origin of the Phonetical Opposition Theory in Linguistics. American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769), 1(10), 624–626. Retrieved from <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/STEM/article/view/2210>

11. Khudoyberdieva Oyjamol Muzaffarovna. (2023). The Role of Dance Terminology in Linguistics. Genius Repository, 26, 83–85. Retrieved from <https://www.geniusrepo.net/index.php/1/article/view/246>